

IDENTIFICATION OF CLAY MINERALS IN THE SOIL USING ATTERBERG LIMIT PARAMETERS

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ABSTRACT

Montmorillonite clay is a problematic soil for both geotechnical and pavement engineers. Therefore, identifying the presence of the expansive montmorillonite clay mineral within the soil matrix using a simple and inexpensive method is of paramount importance. This paper presents a simple method of identifying the primary clay minerals, namely kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite, in the soil matrix using Atterberg limits parameters, namely plasticity index, plastic limit, and slope of the fall cone curve (defined as 20/LL). The proposed methods can be used as a preliminary indicator method of identifying the presence of expansive clay minerals within the soil matrix before carrying out an expensive definitive method of identifying clay minerals, such as XRD.

INTRODUCTION

The amount of clay and the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix largely influence the consistency limits of the soil. Therefore, the consistency limits of the soil can be used as a simple indicator of identifying the predominant clay mineral within the soil matrix.

This paper presents simple charts that can aid the identification of the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix without employing a definitive approach to identifying clay minerals within the soil matrix, such as XRD. The proposed identification methods are based on the position of the soil on the (a) plasticity chart (liquid limit and plasticity index), (b) slope of the fall cone flow curve (20/LL) and plasticity index, (c) the slope of the fall cone flow curve (20/LL) and plastic limit, (d) plastic limit and arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and plastic limit and (e) slope of the fall cone curve (20/LL) and the arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and the plastic limit. The clay identification methods proposed in this paper were developed based on an analysis of published 191 Atterberg limits data of clay soils composed of 64

samples of kaolinite, 16 samples of illite, and 111 montmorillonite samples. Although the liquid limit determined from the Casagrande cup and fall cone method differs, particularly when the liquid limit of soil exceeds 100 [Hrubesova et al. (2016)], for this study, it is assumed that both values are the same.

ATTERBERG LIMITS OF THE CLAY MINERALS

A simple method of identification of clay minerals using a plasticity chart based on the data of Casagrande (1948) and Mitchel (1976) was proposed [Holtz *et al.*, 1981]. In accordance with that study, the montmorillonite clay mineral plots just below the U-line, the illite clay mineral plots just above the A-line, and the kaolinite clay plots just below the A-line.

111 montmorillonite clay Atterberg limits data from literature [Lambe et al., (1979), Karakan, E (1922), Spagnoli *et al.*, 2018, Mishra, K.A, 2012, Bain, J.A (1971)] are plotted on the plasticity chart [Figure 1]. It can be seen that most of the montmorillonite clay plots above the A-line, while some plots below the A-line, particularly ca-montmorillonite clay with a liquid limit of less than 200. Some montmorillonite clay soil samples plot above the U-line, particularly when the liquid limit is more than 500. The liquid limit of the montmorillonite clay is highly correlated to the plasticity index, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.99. The coefficient of determination of 0.99 was also reported by Spagnoli (2018) using 59 Atterberg limits data of smectite, and the linear correlation developed of $PI = 0.97LL - 37.6$ is very close to the equation developed during this study as shown in equation 1.

$$PI = 0.97LL - 44.22 \dots \dots (1)$$

The Illite clay has no use commercially, so published Atterberg limits data is scarce. This study analyzed the plasticity index of 16 illite clay from the literature [Bain, J.A (1971), Lambe et al., (1979), Tasnim, T et al, (2014)]. The illite clay

Atterberg limit data published by Bain, J. A and Lambe et al. are for the pure illite clay minerals with higher liquid limit and plasticity index, plotting below the A-line. The illite clay data published by Tasnim et al. is a mixed clay soil with illite content ranging from 77-89%, has a low plasticity index compared to the pure illite, and plots above the A-Line. The position of the illitic clay on the Casagrande plasticity chart is shown in Figure 2. As for the montmorillonite clay, the plasticity index of the illite clay mineral is linearly correlated with the liquid limit, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.98. Therefore, the plasticity index of the illite clay soil can be estimated from the liquid limit using Equation 2.

$$PI = 0.48LL + 6.13 \dots \dots (2)$$

The Atterberg limits of the 64 kaolinic clay taken from the literature [Lambe *et al.* (1979), Bain, J.A. (1971), Spagnoli *et al.* (2018)] were analyzed. The plot of the kaolinite clay on the plasticity chart is shown in Figure 3, from which it can be seen that most of the Atterberg limits test results are plotting below the A-line, while few plots above the A-line. Figure 3 shows that the plasticity index of the kaolinite clay can also be estimated from the liquid limit using the linear model shown in Equation 3 ($R^2=0.8$).

$$PI = 0.65LL - 8.4 \dots \dots (3)$$

Figure 1: Position of the montmorillonite clay on the plasticity chart

Figure 2: Position of illite clay on the plasticity chart

Figure 3: Position of kaolinite clay on the plasticity chart

CLASSIFICATION OF CLAY MINERALS BASED ON THE PLASTICITY CHART

Figure 4 shows the position of kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite clay on the plasticity chart. For clarity, the liquid limit and plasticity index are plotted to a maximum value of 200 and 140, respectively. It can be seen that the clay minerals plot within a particular region on the plasticity chart. However, the A-Line seems not the best

reference point for delineating the clay minerals, as evidenced by the fact that montmorillonite, illite, and kaolinite clay minerals can plot on either side of the A-Line. However, it is evident that the clay minerals tend to occupy a predefined distinct position on the plasticity chart. The manual best-fit delineation of the kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite clay minerals is shown in Figure 4, from which it can be seen that the kaolinite clay and illite clay may have the same liquid limit, except that the plasticity index of the illite clay would be higher than that of kaolinite clay.

Table 1: Classification accuracy matrix of clay minerals on the plasticity chart

Minerals	Samples	Number classified correct	Classification accuracy
Montmorillonite	111	111	100%
Illite	16	10	62.5%
Kaolinite	64	61	95.3
Total	191	182	95.2%

Figure 4: Position of kaolinite, illite and montmorillonite clay on the plasticity chart

It can also be seen that the pure illite clay and three samples of kaolinite clay plotted within the montmorillonite clay band because of its high liquid limit and plasticity index. The accuracy of this method of delineating the clay mineral on the

plasticity chart is shown in Table 1. The classification accuracy is computed by dividing the number of samples correctly classified by the total number of samples.

CLAY MINERAL SOIL CLASSIFICATIONS BASED ON THE FALL CONE SLOPE OF THE FLOW CURVE (20/LL)

The slope of the fall cone curve is correlated to the plasticity index. Maregesi (2022) reported that the slope of the fall cone flow curve progressively decreases as the moisture content decreases. The slope tends to quasi-stabilize at a penetration value of about 5 mm. Based on this gradual change of slope as the penetration value decreases, Maregesi (2022) proposed to compute the slope of the fall cone curve using Equation 1, whereby the slope of the fall cone curve is computed using penetration values of 25 mm and 5 mm and their corresponding moisture contents respectively. Practically, it is only possible to determine the penetration value and its corresponding moisture content up to a penetration value of about 3mm using the British fall cone. However, this is only due to practical limitations. Suppose it could have been possible to determine the penetration values and their corresponding 0% moisture content. In that case, it can be reasonably postulated that the fall cone slope would continue to decrease as the moisture content decreases. It is hypothesized that as the moisture content of the soil tends to be 0% (dry soil), the fall cone penetration value of the soil would also tend to zero; thus, the ultimate and average slope of the fall cone flow curve is the one that is computed from penetration of 0 mm and its corresponding moisture content of 0 and the liquid limit which corresponds to penetration of 20 mm. This slope is invariant and is the average slope of the fall cone curve, which defines the flow characteristics of the soil and can be computed using Equation 2.

$$S = \frac{25 - 5}{w_{25} - w_5} = \frac{20}{w_{25} - w_5} \dots \dots (4)$$

$$S = \frac{20 - 0}{LL - 0} = \frac{20}{LL} \dots \dots (5)$$

Where:

'S' is the slope of the fall cone flow curve

'W₂₅' is the water content corresponding to a penetration value of 25 mm
 'W₅' is the water content corresponding to a penetration value of 5 mm

The fall cone slope computed using equation (4) is highly correlated to the plasticity index (R²=0.9926) (Maregesi,2022). Similarly, the slope computed using equation 5 is also highly correlated with the plasticity index (Figure 5) with a coefficient of determination (R²) of 0.994 when fitted using the power function model shown in equation 6. It is worth mentioning that despite the fact that most of the Atterberg limits test results analyzed were carried out using the Casagrande cup, yet, the slope of the fall cone is highly correlated with the plasticity index. Therefore, it is postulated that a better correlation could have been achieved if the liquid limit had been determined using the fall cone. Since the slope of the fall cone curve is highly correlated to the plasticity index and the plasticity index of the soil varies depending on the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix, it can be inferred that the slope of the fall cone flow curve can be used as a simple means of identifying the type of clay minerals within the soil matrix.

$$PI = 6.278 \left(\frac{20}{LL} - 0.0092 \right)^{-1.414} \dots \dots (6)$$

Since the slope of the fall cone flow curve (20/LL) varies depending on the mineral composition of the soil, Equation 6 can be used to predict the plasticity index of the soil using liquid limit as the only predictor variable.

The data shown in Figure 5 shows that as the fall cone slope increases, the plasticity index decreases. It can be seen that the soil having a fall cone slope of less than 0.16 is classified as montmorillonite clay, while the fall cone slope of more than 0.6 is for kaolinite clay. Within the intermediate fall cone slope range of 0.15 -0.6 is occupied by both illite and kaolinite clay.

From Figure 5, it can be seen that it is possible to delineate the three different clay minerals, namely kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite, using the slope of the fall cone and plasticity index, particularly when the graph is rescaled to include only soil with a plasticity index of less than 100.

Figure 5: Relationship between the fall cone slope and plasticity index

Figure 6: Classification of different clay minerals based on the slope of the fall cone curve and plasticity index of the soil

Figure 6 shows the classification bands for the different clay minerals in the space of the fall cone slope and plasticity index. Both kaolinite and illite clay minerals of high plasticity are misclassified because they are plotting within the band of montmorillonite clay minerals. The accuracy of this

method in classifying the clay minerals is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Classification accuracy matrix using fall cone slope and plasticity index

Minerals	Samples	Number classified correct	Classification accuracy
Montmorillonite	111	111	100%
Illite	16	9	56.3%
Kaonite	64	56	87.5%
Total	191	176	92.1%

Further data analysis indicated that the clay mineral can be delineated using the slope of the fall cone flow curve and the plastic limit. The delineation was carried out using a machine learning library in R (e1071 package). The classification of the clay minerals using the e1071 package in R is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Classification of clay minerals using the slope of the fall cone and plastic limit (R-package e1071)

Figure 7 classification boundary plot was digitized and improved to reflect the Atterberg limit test results trend. The Atterberg limit data are superimposed on the digitized plot (Figure 8) from which it can be seen that the kaolin clay mineral has a higher value of the plastic limit than that of the illite clay mineral. The summary of the accuracy of this method for classifying the clay minerals is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Classification accuracy matrix using fall cone slope and plastic limit

Minerals	Samples	Number classified correct	Classification accuracy
Montmorillonite	111	109	98.2%
Illite	16	10	62.5%
Kaonite	64	61	95.3%
Total	191	180	94.2%

Figure 8: Delineation of minerals using fall cone slope and plastic limit (the delineation established using machine learning algorithm in R-package e1071)

Furthermore, clay mineral types can also be classified using the plastic limit and the arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and plastic limit. It is revealed that for most cases, the plasticity index of the kaolinite clay is less than the plastic limit. Figure 9 shows the position of the soil on the plot of the plastic limit and the arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and the plastic limit. The accuracy of his method in classifying the clay minerals is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Classification of clay minerals using plastic limit and arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and plastic limit

Minerals	Samples	Number classified correct	Classification accuracy
Montmorillonite	111	105	94.6
Illite	16	16	100%
Kaonite	64	63	98.4
Total	191	184	96.3%

Figure 9: Classification of clay minerals based on the plastic limit and arithmetic difference between plastic limit and plasticity index

The clay minerals can also be classified using the soil position on the plot of the fall cone slope (20/LL) and the arithmetic difference between the plasticity index and plastic limit. The classification of the clay minerals is shown in Figure 10, while the summary of classification accuracy is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Classification of clay minerals

Minerals	Samples	Number classified correct	Classification accuracy
Montmorillonite	111	111	100
Illite	16	9	56.3
Kaonite	64	62	96.9
Total	191	182	95.3

Figure 10: Classification of clay minerals based on the fall cone slope and arithmetic difference between plastic limit and plasticity index

CONCLUSION

Methods of delineating the clay minerals based on the Atterberg limit parameters are presented. Based on the analysis of the 191 Atterberg limits data, it is possible to classify the three clay minerals, namely kaolinite, illite, and montmorillonite, with an accuracy of more than 90%. The proposed methods of classifying clay minerals can be used as a preliminary indicator of identifying the presence of an expansive clay mineral within the soil before embarking on the expensive definitive method of identifying clay within the soil matrix, such as XRD.

References:

1. Bain, J.A, A plasticity chart as an aid to the identification and assessment of industrial clay, clay minerals, 1971
2. Holtz, D.r & Kovacs, D.W, An introduction to geotechnical engineering (1981), Prentice-Hall, Inc

- 3.** Hrubesova, E., Lunackova, B., and Brodzki, O., comparison of liquid limit of soils resulted from Casagrande test and Modified Cone Penetrometer Methodology, *Procedia Engineering*, 142, 364-370, (2016).
- 4.** Karakan, E. Comparative Analysis of Atterberg Limits, Liquidity Index, Flow Index and Undrained Shear Strength Behavior in Binary Clay Mixtures, *Appl. Sci.* 2022, 12, 8616. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12178616>
- 5.** Lambe, W.T & Whitman R.V (1979), *Soil Mechanics*, SI version, John Wiley & Sons
- 6.** Maregesi, G, Determination of the plasticity index using the slope of fall cone flow curve, *Advanced Engineering Solutions Journal*, Vol2/22.
- 7.** Mishra, K.A, Ohtsubo, M, Li, Y.L, Higashi, T (2012), Influence of Various factors on the difference in the liquid limit values determined by Casagrande's and fall cone method, *Environ. Earth Sci*(2012)
- 8.** Tasnim, T, Rana, S, Haque, E, Sayem, H, (2014), Evaluation of Atterberg limits of Barind clay soils of Bogra and their Relationship with clay minerals, *Jahangirnagar University Journal of Science*, Vol 37, No.2, PP 1-17